

1 **Supplementary file for**

2 **Early Oligocene surface uplift in southwestern Montana during North**

3 **American Cordilleran extension**

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12 This file includes:

13 Supplementary Texts S1–S4;

14 Supplementary Tables S1–S3;

15 Supplementary Figures S1–S4;

16 Supplementary Table S4 is a large data table shown in a separate Excel file.

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19 **Text S1. Sedimentology, depositional environment, and depositional ages**

20 ***Sage Creek Basin***

21 Among the 60 glass samples, 23 tuffaceous sandstone and siltstone and two ash-fall tuff
22 samples were collected from the Sage Creek Basin (Table S1). The Renova Formation in the basin
23 includes the Sage Creek, Dell, Cook Ranch, White Hills and Blacktail Creek members (Fig. S1),

24 from the bottom to the top. Except for the Blacktail Creek Member, our samples were collected
25 from the type sections of the other four members (Fig. S2), of which the sedimentology was well
26 studied previously (Schwartz & Graham, 2017; Schwartz et al., 2019). In brief, the lower Sage
27 Creek Member (Fig. S3A) varies from thickly bedded, crudely stratified, granular conglomerates
28 to gravelly sandstones deposited in a debris flow-dominated alluvial fan environment. The upper
29 Sage Creek Member (Fig. S3B) contains thinly bedded, normally graded granular conglomerates,
30 sandstones, and siltstones deposited in a distal, braided to anastomosing river-dominated alluvial
31 fan environment. The Dell (Fig. S3C) and White Hills (Fig. S3D) members contain sandstones,
32 siltstones and sandy mudstones with a minor amount of conglomerate lens and were deposited in
33 a debris flow-dominated alluvial fan environment.

34 The Blacktail Creek Member (Fig. S3E) was not sampled by previous studies. This member
35 is dominated by maroon and gray, fine-grained sandstones and sandy mudstones containing
36 floating medium- to coarse-grained sands or granules. The sandstones and mudstones are mostly
37 massive, but planar beddings occasionally present. Root casts are common. Lenticular well-
38 cemented sandstones of ~1 m thick were also observed. In general, the lithofacies in this member
39 are not different from those in the Dell and White Hills members, and we interpret that the Blacktail
40 Creek Member was also deposited in a debris flow-dominated alluvial fan environment.

41 The Sage Creek Basin contains the best dated strata among all the studied basins in
42 southwestern Montana. Many studies of mammal fossil biostratigraphy, detrital zircon U-Pb
43 maximum depositional ages (MDAs), and zircon U-Pb ages of interlayered volcanic rocks have
44 been conducted (Fields et al., 1985; Tabrum et al., 1996; Kent-Corson et al., 2006; Fritz et al.,
45 2007; Methner et al., 2016; Schwartz & Graham, 2017; Schwartz et al., 2019). In brief, the lower
46 Sage Creek Member is deposited between 48–47 Ma and the upper Sage Creek Member is between

47 47–46 Ma, the Dell Member is between 45–40 Ma, the Cook Ranch Member is between 36–30
48 Ma, the White Hills Member is between 30–25 Ma, and the Blacktail Creek Member is between
49 25–20 Ma (see summary in Schwartz et al., 2019).

50 The MDA of our new detrital zircon sample from the Cook Ranch Member is 31.9 ± 0.2 Ma
51 (Table 1), consistent with previously determined age range of the member (36–30 Ma). One of the
52 two Blacktail Creek Member sandstone samples yields a MDA of 23.8 ± 0.3 Ma (Table 1),
53 consistent with the depositional age of the Blacktail Creek Member (25–20 Ma) (Schwartz et al.,
54 2019).

55 ***Muddy Creek Basin***

56 A total of six tuffaceous sandstone and tuff samples were collected from the Renova Formation
57 in the Muddy Creek Basin. The basin is a small normal fault-controlled half graben and the
58 sedimentology has been studied in detail (e.g., Janecke et al., 1999). The lithofacies include ash-
59 flow tuffs and lava-flows (Tcv facies) and pebble to boulder conglomerates and minor sandstones
60 and mudstones (Tcg facies) deposited by a eastward or southeastward regional river system at the
61 bottom of the formation. These two facies are interbedded intimately and filled paleo-valleys
62 formed at the margin of the Challis volcanic field. Above the Tcv and Tcg strata, well-laminated
63 tabular-shaped tuffaceous shales (Tts facies; Fig. S4A) changes to organic-rich shales (Tos facies)
64 in the basin center. Both facies were deposited in lacustrine to palustrine depositional
65 environments. The last facies contains interbedded pebble- to cobble-conglomerates, sandstones
66 and mudstones (Tcs facies; Fig. S4B) that were deposited in small alluvial fans and fan-deltas. The
67 Tcs facies were first deposited at the basin margin, coeval with the lacustrine strata of Tts and Tos,
68 both of which transited into the Tcs facies toward the top of the Renova Formation.

69 Strata in the Muddy Creek Basin (Table S1) were studied for mammal fossils and gastropod
70 assemblages (Dunlap, 1982; Dascoli et al., 1996) and three sanidine $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dates were also
71 reported for two tuffs from the Tcv facies and one from the lower Tts unit (Janecke et al., 1999).
72 These ages are well summarized in Janecke et al. (1999). The bottom unit (interbedded Tcv and
73 Tcg facies) was deposited between 49.5–45.5 Ma. Ages of our three glass samples collected near
74 the top of the Tcv facies were assigned to be between 46.5 and 45.5 Ma, with errors of ± 2.5 Ma.
75 Age of the sample collected from the middle part of the lacustrine unit (Tts facies) was assigned
76 to be 40 ± 5 Ma because the unit is roughly between 45–37 Ma. Ages of the post-tectonic basalt
77 flow and basaltic plug near the northern continuation of the Muddy–Grasshopper detachment fault
78 indicate that tilting on the Muddy Creek fault system had ended by 27.6 Ma (Janecke et al., 1999),
79 suggesting that deposition of the Tcs unit ended by 27.6 Ma. We thus assign the two samples
80 collected from the upper part of the Tcs facies to be 30 ± 5 and 29 ± 5 Ma, respectively.

81 ***Big Hole Valley***

82 Two tuff samples were collected from the Renova Formation in the Big Hole Valley. One is
83 from the Jackson North section and the other is from the Chalk Bluff section of Roe (2010). The
84 Jackson North section (Fig. S4H) contains contorted and vertically-tilted tuffs and tuffaceous
85 sandstones with floating granules deposited in a sandy debris flow-dominated alluvial fan
86 environment (Roe, 2010). The Chalk Bluff section (Fig. S4G) is less deformed, and dominated by
87 tuffaceous mudstones containing floating sand or granule grains that were deposited in a muddy
88 debris flow-dominated alluvial fan environment (Roe, 2010).

89 The sample from the Jackson North section was previously dated by high-resolution zircon
90 U-Pb TIMS dating and the age is 26.16 ± 0.04 Ma (Roe, 2010). The Chalk Bluff section was
91 considered to be Oligocene in age based on a single mammal tooth fragment (Hanneman & Nichols,

92 1981). At a site two miles northwest of the Chalk Bluff section, a basanite lava yielded a K-Ar age
93 of 21.9 ± 0.3 Ma (Fritz et al., 2007), which was considered to be younger than the Chalk Bluff
94 rocks (Roe, 2010). Our sample was collected near the top of the Chalk Bluff section, and the age
95 was assigned to be 25 ± 5 Ma.

96 *Flint Creek Basin*

97 A total of four tuffaceous sandstone samples were collected from the Renova Formation of
98 the Flint Creek Basin. Two of them are from the Garnet Range Member and the other two from
99 the overlying Cabbage Patch Member. The Garnet Range Member (Fig. S4C) is poorly outcropped,
100 and where it is outcropped, it contains white, massive, tuffaceous siltstones (Portner et al., 2011).
101 The Cabbage Patch Member (Fig. S4D) contains interbedded dark-gray, massive, fine-grained
102 tuffaceous sandstones, mudstones, and some thin carbonate beds of ~5 cm thick. The mudstones
103 contain abundant molds of gastropods and snails (Fig. S4D). The Garnet Range Member and
104 Cabbage Patch Member were most likely deposited in alluvial fan environment and lacustrine
105 environment, respectively (Portner et al., 2011).

106 The Cabbage Patch Member was dated to be between 29.5 and 23.5 Ma by
107 magnetostratigraphy and sanidine $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating of volcanic rocks (Rasmuseen & Prothero,
108 2003; Portner et al., 2011). Our two Cabbage Patch samples were collected a few meters above
109 the 27 Ma volcanic rock in the CBY section of Portner et al. (2011), and the ages were assigned to
110 be 26 ± 3 Ma and 25 ± 3 Ma, respectively. The Garnet Range Member is of the Chadronian North
111 American Lang Mammal Stage (Rasmuseen & Prothero, 2003), whose age is between 37.0–33.9
112 Ma. Thus, the ages of the two samples from this member were assigned to be 36 ± 2 and 35 ± 2
113 Ma, respectively, given that they were collected from the middle part of the member.

114 *Upper Jefferson Basin*

115 A total of nine samples, including five tuff and four tuffaceous sandstone samples, were
116 collected from the Renova Formation and its overlying Sixmile Creek Formation in the Upper
117 Jefferson Basin. The five tuff samples were provided by Dr. Debra Hanneman; and three of the
118 four tuffaceous sandstone samples were collected stratigraphically above or below the tuff samples.
119 The Renova Formation of the Upper Jefferson Basin includes mainly three members: the Climbing
120 Arrow Member, the Dunbar Creek Member and the Bone Basin Member (Kuenzi & Fields, 1971;
121 Vuke et al., 2004); other informal members, such as the Negro Hollow Member, were also used
122 (Vuke et al., 2004; Schwartz et al., 2019).

123 Two of our Renova Formation samples were collected from the Climbing Arrow Member in
124 the Pipestone locality (Fig. S3H), and the member in this locality is dominated by interbedded
125 mudstones and lenticular, fine-grained sandstones that were deposited in a fluvial environment
126 (Tabrum et al., 1996; Retallack, 2007; Schwartz et al., 2019). Two of our Renova Formation
127 samples were collected from the Dunbar Creek Member in the Palisades Cliffs locality (Fig. S3F),
128 and the member is dominated by interbedded fine- to coarse-grained sandstones with floating
129 granules and pebbles, tuffs, and lenses of conglomerates (Kuenzi & Fields, 1971; Vuke et al.,
130 2004). These strata were mainly deposited in small alluvial fan environments along basin margins
131 (Kuenzi & Fields, 1971; Schwartz & Schwartz, 2013). Three of our Renova Formation samples
132 were collected from the Bone Basin Member in the Lazy TP locality (Fig. S3G). The member here
133 contains mostly coarse-grained, tuffaceous sandstones with scour surfaces and a few limestone
134 beds of ~20 cm thick. The sandstones are extensively mottled, contain root casts as large as 8 mm
135 in diameter and calcrete nodules. The top of the member contains sandy limestones with root casts,
136 and the limestones were formed either by coalesced paleosol nodules or calcrete (Alonso-Zarza,
137 2003; Tabor et al., 2017). It is inferred that the member was also deposited in a fluvial-dominated

138 environment with extensive pedogenesis (Schwartz et al., 2019). We also have two samples
139 collected from the Sixmile Creek Formation in this basin. The formation is dominated by coarse-
140 grained sandstones and conglomerates in both basin center (Lazy TP locality) and basin margin
141 (Palisades locality), and has been interpreted to be deposited by a transverse fluvial and an alluvial
142 fan depositional environment, respectively (Kuenzi & Fields, 1971; Sears et al., 2009).

143 Fossils of the Chadronian (37.0–33.9 Ma) and Orellan (33.9–31.8) North America Land
144 Mammal Ages have been reported from the Climbing Arrow Member and Dunbar Creek Member,
145 respectively (Kuenzi & Fields, 1971; Axelrod, 1984; Tabrum et al., 1996). Field observations also
146 indicate that the Dunbar Creek Member overlies the Climbing Arrow Member (Kuenzi & Fields,
147 1971). The top of the Bone Basin Member was constrained to be 24.9 ± 1.9 Ma by a detrital zircon
148 U-Pb maximum depositional age (Schwartz et al., 2019). The bottom of the Bone Basin Member
149 is not well determined, and may be older than 32 Ma (Kuenzi & Fields, 1971). Based on these age
150 constraints, the ages of the samples from the three members were constrained to be between 37–
151 34 Ma, 34–32 Ma, and 32–25 Ma, respectively. The Sixmile Creek Formation was determined to
152 be 16.3–2.6 Ma based on vertebrate fossil ages (Kuenzi & Fields, 1971). The tuffaceous sandstone
153 and tuff samples collected near the base of the Formation were thus assigned to be 16 ± 3 Ma and
154 15 ± 3 Ma, respectively. These ages agree with unpublished sanidine and plagioclase $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$
155 ages of the ongoing project of Dr. Debra Hanneman (personal communication, 2017).

156 ***Smith River Basin***

157 Two samples were collected from two individual locations of the Renova Formation in the
158 Smith River Basin. The first one is a ~4 m thick road-cut (Fig. S4F), which is dominated by brown,
159 massive, tuffaceous siltstones with floating pebbles up to 6 mm in diameter. The other location is
160 a ~12 m thick cliff (Fig. S4E), which contains mainly brown, massive, tuffaceous siltstones and

161 dark gray, lenticular sandstone bodies with scour surfaces and cross-beddings. Root traces and
162 carbonate nodules are common in the siltstones. These rocks were most likely deposited in a fluvial
163 environment.

164 This study reports a detrital zircon U-Pb maximum depositional age of 30.4 ± 0.7 Ma (Table
165 1) for one of the two samples. The age of the other sample was assigned to 27 ± 5 Ma because the
166 strata in this basin were suggested to be deposited during the Oligocene based on lithofacies
167 similarity with the Oligocene strata in the adjacent basins (Reynolds & Brandt, 2005).

168 ***Upper Ruby, Three Forks, Canyon Ferry basins and Gravelly Range***

169 Volcanic glass samples from these basins are all tuff samples (Table S1) provided by Dr.
170 Debra Hanneman. Below we provide a generalized description of lithofacies and depositional
171 environment, as well as determination of depositional ages based on literatures.

172 ***Upper Ruby Basin:***

173 Four samples were collected from the Upper Ruby Basin, including one sample from the
174 Passamari Member of the Renova Formation and three samples from the Anderson Ranch Member
175 of the Sixmile Creek Formation (Fig. 2). The Renova Formation in the Upper Ruby Basin includes
176 three different members, including, from the bottom to the top, the Climbing Arrow, Dunbar Creek
177 and Passamari members. The Climbing Arrow and Dunbar Creek members contain mainly fine-
178 grained sandstones and mudstones deposited in fluvial environments (Monroe, 1981; Lielke &
179 Thomas, 2012). The Passamari Member contains both fine-grained sandstones, mudstones and
180 limestones deposited in a shallow lake environment, as well as coarse-grained sandstones and
181 conglomerates deposited in marginal lacustrine and alluvial environments (Monroe, 1981). Based
182 on vertebrate fossils, it has been suggested that the Climbing Arrow Member was deposited in the

183 Chadronian (37–33.9 Ma), and the Passamari Member was deposited in the Arikareean (~30–20
184 Ma) (Monroe, 1981).

185 The Sixmile Creek Formation in the Upper Ruby Basin was further divided into, from the
186 bottom to the top, the Sweetwater Creek Member, Anderson Ranch Member and Big Hole River
187 Member (Fritz & Sears, 1993). Dating of volcanic rocks of the Anderson Ranch Member indicates
188 the depositional age of the member is between 16 and 6 Ma (Fritz & Sears, 1993). The three
189 Anderson Ranch samples were collected from different locations and it is impossible to correlate
190 them. We assigned 11 ± 5 Ma, the age range of the member, to the three samples.

191 ***Three Forks Basin:***

192 Four tuff samples were collected from the Three Forks Basin. Three of the samples are from
193 the Dunbar Creek Member of the Renova Formation and one is from the lowest Sixmile Creek
194 Formation following regional geological map (Vuke et al., 2002). The Dunbar Creek Member is
195 dominated by tuffaceous siltstones and fine-grained sandstones with isolated coarse-grained
196 sandstone and conglomerate lens; while the Sixmile Creek Member consists mainly conglomerates
197 and conglomeratic sandstones (Vuke et al., 2002). Previous studies suggested that both the Dunbar
198 Creek Member and the Sixmile Creek Formation were deposited in fluvial-dominated
199 environments (Robinson, 1961; Vuke et al., 2002).

200 A K-Ar date of 30.6 ± 1.2 Ma was reported for the Dunbar Creek Member (Hughes, 1980).
201 A plagioclase ^{40}Ar - ^{39}Ar date in the member indicates deposition during the earliest Miocene
202 (personal communication with Debra Hanneman, 2017). We thus consider the Dunbar Creek
203 Member of the Three Forks Basin was deposited during the late Oligocene to early Miocene (~30–
204 20 Ma). The age of the Dunbar Creek sample in the northern basin was assigned to be 25 ± 5 Ma,
205 and the ages of the other two samples collected in the basin center were assigned to be 26 ± 5 Ma

206 and 27 ± 5 Ma, respectively. For the Sixmile Creek Formation, in addition to Barstovian mammal
207 fossils, a K-Ar date of 8.9 ± 0.4 Ma was also reported (Hughes, 1980).

208 ***Canyon Ferry Basin:***

209 Three different rock units were identified for the Renova Formation in the Canyon Ferry
210 Basin, from the bottom to the top, they are the Climbing Arrow Member, Dunbar Creek Member
211 and White Earth unit (Vuke et al., 2011). Two samples were collected from this basin with one
212 from the Climbing Arrow Member and the other from the White Earth Unit. Both the Climbing
213 Arrow Member and White Earth Unit are dominated by mudstones, while the former also includes
214 lenses of sandstones and conglomerates (Vuke et al., 2011). It has been suggested that the Climbing
215 Arrow Member was deposited in a fluvial environment, while the White Earth unit was deposited
216 in a lacustrine environment (White, 1954; CoBabe et al., 2002; Vuke et al., 2011).

217 Vertebrate fossils indicate that these three units were deposited during the Chadronian (37.0–
218 33.9 Ma), Orellan (33.9–31.8 Ma), and Arikareean (~30–20 Ma) (White, 1954; CoBabe et al.,
219 2002). The ages of our two samples from the Climbing Arrow Member and White Earth Unit were
220 assigned to be 34 ± 2 Ma and 27 ± 5 Ma, respectively.

221 ***Gravelly Range:***

222 One tuff sample was collected on top of the Gravelly Range. The unit contains mainly
223 volcanic and volcanoclastic rocks that were deposited in a small alluvial fan between the Black
224 Butte and Lion mountains (Gutmann et al., 1989). This study reports a zircon U-Pb age of $31.1 \pm$
225 0.1 Ma for the tuff sample (Table 1), consistent with a previously reported biotite K-Ar age of 31.4
226 ± 0.7 Ma (Gutmann et al., 1989).

227

228

229 **Text S2. Stable hydrogen isotope analysis of volcanic glass**

230 All glass samples were gently crushed using ceramic mortar and pestle, and treated with
231 weak hydrochloric acid (<2N) to remove carbonates. After washing the samples several times to
232 neutralize pH, samples were wet sieved for the 63–125 μm fraction. After drying this fraction,
233 glass shards were separated out using LST heavy liquid with a density of 2.3–2.4 g/ml. Dried glass
234 shards were then treated with 5% hydrofluoric acid for ~30 seconds to remove surface that may
235 have been altered into clays. A hand magnet and Frantz isodynamic magnetic separator were also
236 used to remove magnetic impurities. These pretreatments yield glass shards with >95 % purity.

237 Approximately 1.5–2 mg of pure glass shards, depending on water content, were enclosed in
238 silver foil, and then immediately flushed with dry helium gas within a zero-blank auto-sampler.
239 Samples were combusted at 1450 °C in the glass carbon reduction furnace of a Finnegan TC/EA,
240 and the reducing hydrogen gas was carried by dry helium gas into a Finnegan Delta V mass
241 spectrometer for hydrogen isotope analysis. The analyses were conducted in the Environmental
242 Isotope Laboratory at the University of Arizona. One in-house working standard (Benzoic Acid)
243 was ran with the samples to monitor daily drift of the thermal combustion reactor. Two
244 internationally referenced standard materials, NBS-30 biotite and IAEA-CH7 Polyethylene, were
245 also ran with the samples to calibrate the raw data for mass bias and offset from the certified
246 reference values. Random samples were duplicated and tested for consistency. The calibration
247 linearity was checked by C₃₆ *n*-alkane standard ($\delta\text{D} = -246.7 \pm 1.4 \text{‰}$) from the Indiana University.
248 Repeated measurements of various standards and unknowns yielded a precision of 2.0 ‰ (1 σ) or
249 better for δD values. All the δD values were reported relative to Vienna Standard Mean Ocean
250 Water (VSMOW). Water contents of glass samples were calibrated to NBS-30, which has a water
251 content of 3.5 wt.%. Repeated measurements of NBS-30 yield a precision of 0.2 wt.% (1 σ) for

252 water content. Each sample was analyzed twice and the average of the two volcanic glass hydrogen
253 isotopic values (δD_{vg}) and water contents are listed in Table S1 (data summary) and Table S2 (all
254 raw isotopic data).

255

256 **Text S3. XRF major element analysis of selected tuff samples**

257 Major elements of nine randomly selected tuff samples were studied. Approximately $2.00 \pm$
258 $0.02g$ of fine glass material from each sample was weighed and placed in a furnace at $900^{\circ}C$ for
259 1.5 to 2 hrs. Upon removal from the furnace, the sample powders were re-weighed and their loss
260 on ignition (LOI) was calculated. Glass disks were made from the powders by furnace fusion. A
261 flux containing 49.75% lithium tetraborate ($Li_2B_4O_7$), 49.75% lithium metaborate ($LiBO_3$), and
262 0.5% lithium bromide ($LiBr$) was used to reduce inter-element effect (matrix effect) and eliminate
263 particle size effect. Oxidized sample powders and the flux were dried at $110^{\circ}C$ for more than 24
264 hours, then $0.75 \pm 0.002g$ of sample and $8.25 \pm 0.002g$ of flux were mixed into a crucible for
265 fusion. The crucible was made by alloy containing 95% platinum and 5% gold and has a diameter
266 of 32mm. The fused samples were then poured directly into Pt-Au molds and allowed to quench
267 to room temperature for 10 minutes. Fused glass disks of eight international rock standard
268 reference materials (i.e., AGV-2, BHVO-2, JB-2, JGb-2, JSy-1, JR-3, JP-1, and GSP-2) were also
269 analyzed to create the calibration curve for samples. The statistical average of five measurements
270 on each standard was used in the calibration curves, which has correlation coefficients (r^2) varying
271 from 0.9994 to 1.0. Reproducibility of the method was checked by repeated measurements ($N =$
272 10) of international standards BCR-2, BIR-1a, JA-2, JG-3, and W-2. Accuracies of all the
273 measurement are less than 1.0%. The reported element concentrations of the samples are the

274 averages of triplicate analyses. The content of SiO₂ varies between 64% and 74% after correction
275 of loss on ignition. All major element data are listed in Table S3.

276

277 **Text S4. Zircon U-Pb age analysis**

278 Zircon U-Pb ages were measured at the Radiogenic Isotope and Geochronology Lab (RIGL)
279 in the Washington State University using a New Wave 213 nm solid state (Nd:YAG) laser ablation
280 system coupled with a ThermoFinnigan Element 2 single-collector inductively coupled plasma
281 mass spectrometry. Laser spots were 20-30 μm depending on the size of the zircon grains. For
282 each analysis, the first ~6 seconds of data produced, as the sample signal reaches maximum signal
283 intensity, were not considered. The next ~30 seconds of data were used to calculate U-Th-Pb
284 isotope ratios by measuring the intensities of masses ²⁰²Hg, ²⁰⁴Pb+Hg, ²⁰⁶Pb, ²⁰⁷Pb, ²⁰⁸Pb, ²³²Th,
285 ²³⁵U and ²³⁸U during ~300 sweeps through the mass range. Analyses of zircon unknowns and
286 quality control zircon grains were interspersed with analyses of external calibration standards,
287 typically with 10-12 unknowns bracketed by multiple analyses of two different zircon standards
288 (Plešovice and FC-1). The Plešovice standard (337 Ma; Sláma et al., 2008) was used to calibrate
289 the ²⁰⁶Pb/²³⁸U and ²⁰⁷Pb/²³⁵U ages, and the FC-1 standard (1099 Ma; Paces & Miller Jr, 1993) was
290 used for calibration of ²⁰⁷Pb/²⁰⁶Pb ages owing to its high count rate for ²⁰⁷Pb (~2-4 times higher
291 than that of Plešovice). Final ages were determined using a standard-sample bracketing approach.
292 The concentrations of U, Th, Pb were estimated by interspersing analyses of NIST610 glass which
293 has well characterized concentrations of these elements. The U-Pb data reduction protocol follows
294 Chang et al. (2006). Errors of zircon U-Pb ages are reported as 2σ standard deviation. ²⁰⁷Pb/²⁰⁶Pb
295 ages were used for grains older than 900 Ma and ²⁰⁶Pb/²³⁸U ages were used for grains younger than
296 900 Ma. A 20% discordance and a 5% reverse discordance filter were applied to grains older than

297 400 Ma to exclude grains that may have been influenced by Pb loss. Samples 17GR01, 17SR04,
298 17SC52, 17SC60, 17SC64 yield 44, 55, 76, 89 and 87 concordant zircon ages, respectively. See
299 Table S4 for all data.

300

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Table S1. Stable hydrogen isotopic values of Cenozoic volcanic glass and reconstructed paleo-meteoric water from southwestern Montana

ID[†]	Site #	Stratigraphy[‡]	Depositional environment[‡]	Lat. (°N)	Log. (°W)	Elev. (m)	Age (Ma)	error (Ma)	δD_{vg} (‰)	std (‰)	H₂O (wt. %)	δD_{mw}* (‰)
17SC12	SC	Lower Sage Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.741	-112.591	1912	47.8	0.5	-134.1	1.9	1.9	-104.4
17SC14	SC	Lower Sage Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.741	-112.591	1919	47.6	0.5	-143.8	1.2	3.1	-114.4
17SC17	SC	Lower Sage Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.741	-112.591	1919	47.4	0.5	-138.2	0.9	2.0	-108.6
17SC19	SC	Lower Sage Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.741	-112.591	1919	47.2	0.5	-137.6	2.1	4.2	-108.0
17SC27	SC	Upper Sage Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.758	-112.597	1987	46.8	0.5	-150.4	0.9	1.7	-121.3
17SC28	SC	Upper Sage Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.758	-112.597	1987	46.7	0.5	-161.5	1.2	1.1	-132.7
17SC29	SC	Upper Sage Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.758	-112.597	1987	46.6	0.5	-157.8	1.2	2.8	-128.9
17SC30	SC	Upper Sage Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.758	-112.597	1987	46.4	0.5	-158.4	1.2	5.4	-129.5
<u>17SC32</u>	SC	Lower Dell M.	Alluvial fan	44.758	-112.597	1997	44.5	2.0	-92.3	2.1	5.1	-61.2
<u>17SC33</u>	SC	Lower Dell M.	Alluvial fan	44.758	-112.597	1997	44.4	2.0	-126.7	2.1	6.4	-96.7
17SC34	SC	Lower Dell M.	Alluvial fan	44.759	-112.598	2017	43.5	2.0	-131.7	1.2	1.3	-101.9
17SC39	SC	Upper Dell M.	Alluvial fan	44.752	-112.580	1969	43.0	2.0	-137.9	1.8	6.4	-108.3
17SC41	SC	Upper Dell M.	Alluvial fan	44.752	-112.580	1977	41.5	2.0	-153.0	2.1	7.2	-123.9
17SC42	SC	Upper Dell M.	Alluvial fan	44.752	-112.580	1977	41.0	2.0	-152.6	1.8	5.9	-123.5
17SC43	SC	Upper Dell M.	Alluvial fan	44.752	-112.580	1977	40.5	2.0	-151.6	2.1	5.3	-122.5
17SC47	SC	Cook Ranch M.	Alluvial fan	44.750	-112.567	1947	34.5	2.0	-172.0	1.8	4.6	-143.6
17SC49	SC	Cook Ranch M.	Alluvial fan	44.750	-112.567	1957	34.0	2.0	-173.1	1.8	2.4	-144.7
17SC51	SC	Cook Ranch M.	Alluvial fan	44.750	-112.567	1969	33.0	2.0	-170.2	2.1	6.2	-141.7
17SC52	SC	Cook Ranch M.	Alluvial fan	44.750	-112.567	1969	31.9	0.2	-171.2	0.7	5.5	-142.8
17SC54	SC	Cook Ranch M.	Alluvial fan	44.750	-112.567	1995	31.0	2.0	-181.4	1.8	5.7	-153.3
17SC60	SC	Blacktail Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.847	-112.539	2068	23.8	0.3	-196.7	1.8	4.6	-169.1
17SC61	SC	Blacktail Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.847	-112.539	2074	23.0	2.0	-176.9	1.8	2.8	-148.7
17SC62	SC	Blacktail Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.847	-112.539	2074	22.5	2.0	-190.5	1.8	5.1	-162.7
17SC63	SC	Blacktail Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.847	-112.539	2074	22.0	2.0	-175.0	0.7	3.7	-146.7
17SC64	SC	Blacktail Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.847	-112.539	2087	21.0	2.0	-159.4	0.7	5.4	-130.6
17SC66	SC	Blacktail Creek M.	Alluvial fan	44.847	-112.539	2087	20.0	2.0	-72.5	1.8	2.2	-40.7
<u>17MC02</u>	MC	Tcv volcanic rocks	Alluvial fan	44.744	-112.897	2343	46.5	2.5	-79.7	0.9	4.0	-48.1
<u>17MC04</u>	MC	Tcv volcanic rocks	Alluvial fan	44.742	-112.892	2247	46.0	2.5	-76.4	0.9	5.5	-44.7
<u>17MC05</u>	MC	Tcv volcanic rocks	Alluvial fan	44.740	-112.891	2217	45.5	2.5	-77.6	0.9	6.0	-46.0

<u>17MC11</u>	MC	Tts tuffaceous shale	Lacustrine	44.660	-112.848	2083	40.0	5.0	-143.8	0.9	10.1	-114.4
17MC16	MC	Tcs sandstone	Alluvial fan	44.648	-112.814	2059	27.0	5.0	-108.4	0.9	1.3	-77.8
17MC17	MC	Tcs sandstone	Alluvial fan	44.648	-112.814	2059	26.0	5.0	-94.5	0.9	1.5	-63.4
17SR02	SR	Renova Fm. undivided	Fluvial	46.651	-111.094	1428	25.0	5.0	-160.7	1.9	6.3	-131.9
17SR04	SR	Renova Fm. undivided	Fluvial	46.714	-111.132	1426	30.4	0.7	-183.5	1.7	8.1	-155.5
<u>RT12-2015</u>	CF	White Earth M.	Lacustrine	46.518	-111.587	1175	27.0	5.0	-164.4	3.2	6.3	-135.8
<u>RT18-2016</u>	CF	Climbing Arrow M.	Fluvial	46.529	-111.622	1159	34.0	2.0	-171.1	1.6	5.6	-142.6
<u>17BH05</u>	BH	Renova Fm. undivided	Alluvial fan	45.438	-113.448	1933	26.0	1.0	-172.9	1.7	6.0	-144.5
<u>17BH16</u>	BH	Renova Fm. undivided	Alluvial fan	45.827	-113.297	1862	25.0	5.0	-165.8	1.7	6.6	-137.2
17FC02	FC	Garnet Range M.	Alluvial fan	46.649	-113.206	1275	36.0	2.0	-150.9	1.7	5.8	-121.8
17FC07	FC	Garnet Range M.	Alluvial fan	46.649	-113.206	1275	35.0	2.0	-166.8	1.7	6.8	-138.2
17FC09	FC	Cabbage Patch M.	Lacustrine	46.595	-113.112	1303	26.0	3.0	-178.1	2.1	5.4	-149.9
17FC12	FC	Cabbage Patch M.	Lacustrine	46.597	-113.111	1298	25.0	3.0	-175.0	2.1	5.5	-146.7
17JB10	JB	Climbing Arrow M.	Transverse fluvial	45.895	-112.262	1461	35.0	2.0	-158.0	2.1	5.6	-129.1
<u>RT9-2015</u>	JB	Climbing Arrow M.	Transverse fluvial	45.894	-112.262	1458	36.0	2.0	-144.1	3.2	6.6	-114.8
<u>RT13-2015</u>	JB	Dunbar Creek M.	Alluvial fan	45.921	-112.212	1521	33.5	1.0	-166.5	3.2	8.1	-137.9
<u>RT14-2015</u>	JB	Dunbar Creek M.	Alluvial fan	45.921	-112.212	1510	32.5	1.0	-146.4	3.2	7.7	-117.2
17JB22	JB	Bone Basin M.	Transverse fluvial	45.806	-112.079	1418	28.0	3.0	-125.3	2.1	5.8	-95.3
<u>RT11-2015</u>	JB	Bone Basin M.	Transverse fluvial	45.807	-112.078	1428	27.0	3.0	-155.4	3.2	6.9	-126.4
17JB32	JB	Bone Basin M.	Transverse fluvial	45.806	-112.079	1442	26.0	3.0	-93.2	2.1	4.0	-62.1
<u>RT10-2015</u>	JB	Sixmile Creek Fm.	Transverse fluvial	45.807	-112.077	1446	16.0	3.0	-164.4	3.2	5.8	-135.7
<u>17JB17</u>	JB	Sixmile Creek Fm.	Alluvial fan	45.921	-112.212	1545	15.0	3.0	-124.0	2.1	8.4	-94.0
<u>RT1-2015</u>	TF	Sixmile Creek Fm.	fluvial	45.665	-111.298	1525	16.0	3.0	-175.8	3.2	6.3	-147.5
<u>RT2-2015</u>	TF	Dunbar Creek M.	fluvial	45.790	-111.472	1315	26.0	5.0	-165.6	3.2	6.6	-137.0
<u>RT5-2015</u>	TF	Dunbar Creek M.	fluvial	45.957	-111.522	1339	25.0	5.0	-181.7	3.2	7.2	-153.7
<u>RT17-2015</u>	TF	Dunbar Creek M.	fluvial	45.780	-111.470	1303	27.0	5.0	-153.3	1.6	6.0	-124.3
<u>TVI</u>	UR	Sixmile Creek Fm.	fluvial	45.032	-112.131	1922	11.0	5.0	-152.0	1.6	6.9	-122.9
<u>TVM</u>	UR	Sixmile Creek Fm.	fluvial	44.917	-112.202	2271	11.0	5.0	-171.5	1.6	4.4	-143.0
<u>TVN</u>	UR	Sixmile Creek Fm.	fluvial	44.919	-112.203	2271	11.0	5.0	-164.6	1.6	4.5	-135.9
<u>TVR</u>	UR	Passamari M.	Lacustrine	44.893	-112.357	2094	27.0	5.0	-104.9	1.6	3.9	-74.2
<u>17GR01</u>	GR	Renova Fm. undivided	Alluvial fan	44.885	-111.798	2932	31.1	0.2	-188.3	0.7	5.7	-160.5

Notes: δD_{vg} and δD_{mw} are the stable hydrogen isotope of volcanic glass and reconstructed paleo-meteoric water, respectively. All isotope data are reported relative to Vienna Standard Mean Ocean Water (VSMOW). See Table S2 for all raw stable hydrogen isotope data.

† Samples with underlines are tuffs, other samples are tuffaceous siltstones or sandstones.

SC, Sage Creek Basin; MC, Muddy Creek Basin; SR, Smith River Basin; CF, Canyon Ferry Basin; BH, Big Hole Valley; FC, Flint Creek Basin; JB, Jefferson Basin; TF, Three Folk Basin; UR, Upper Ruby Basin; GR, Gravelly Range.

‡ Abbreviations: Fm., Formation; M., Member; ND, Not determined.

* Calculated as $\delta D_{mw} = 1.0343 * (1000 + \delta D_{vg}) - 1000$ (Friedman et al., 1993).

Table S2. Raw stable hydrogen isotopic data of volcanic glass

Sample ID	H ₂ O (wt. %)	δD_{vg} (‰)	H ₂ O mean (wt. %)	δD_{vg} mean (‰)	Sample ID	H ₂ O (wt. %)	δD_{vg} (‰)	H ₂ O mean (wt. %)	δD_{vg} mean (‰)
17BH05	5.8	-168.9			17SC41	7.3	-152.7		
17BH05	5.9	-172.9			17SC41	7.1	-153.3	7.2	-153.0
17BH05	6.1	-172.9	6.0	-172.9	17SC42	5.9	-153.2		
17BH16	6.8	-166.4			17SC42	5.9	-152.1	5.9	-152.6
17BH16	6.5	-165.1	6.6	-165.8	17SC43	5.6	-150.8		
17FC02	5.8	-151.4			17SC43	5.1	-152.4	5.3	-151.6
17FC02	5.8	-150.4	5.8	-150.9	17SC47	4.1	-171.6		
17FC07	6.7	-166.4			17SC47	4.9	-172.4	4.5	-172.0
17FC07	6.9	-167.1	6.8	-166.8	17SC49	2.2	-174.2		
17FC09	5.5	-172.5			17SC49	2.3	-171.9	2.3	-173.0
17FC09	5.4	-177.2			17SC51	6.6	-170.1		
17FC09	5.5	-179.0	5.4	-178.1	17SC51	5.9	-170.2	6.2	-170.2
17FC12	5.6	-175.7			17SC52	5.5	-167.4		
17FC12	5.4	-174.3	5.5	-175.0	17SC52	6.0	-170.5		
17GR01	5.4	-187.8			17SC52	4.9	-171.9	5.5	-171.2
17GR01	6.0	-188.8	5.7	-188.3	17SC54	5.8	-180.8		
17JB10	5.6	-158.6			17SC54	5.4	-182.0	5.6	-182.0
17JB10	5.7	-157.3	5.6	-158.0	17SC60	4.5	-193.9		
17JB17	8.4	-125.4			17SC60	4.5	-196.3		
17JB17	8.5	-122.6	8.4	-124.0	17SC60	4.4	-197.0	4.5	-195.7
17JB22	5.6	-121.6			17SC61	3.2	-181.1		
17JB22	5.8	-123.8			17SC61	2.7	-176.3	2.9	-178.7
17JB22	5.8	-126.8	5.8	-125.3	17SC62	4.9	-189.9		
17JB32	3.9	-95.2			17SC62	4.9	-191.0	4.9	-191.0
17JB32	4.0	-91.1	4.0	-93.2	17SC63	3.8	-175.3		
17JB32	3.7	-72.9			17SC63	3.7	-174.7	3.7	-175.0
17JB32	3.8	-70.2	3.7	-71.6	17SC64	5.4	-159.4		
17MC02	4.3	-92.3			17SC64	5.4	-159.4	5.4	-159.4
17MC02	4.0	-95.6			17SC66	2.0	-74.9		
17MC02	4.0	-94.4	4.1	-94.1	17SC66	1.8	-70.8	1.9	-73.0
17MC04	6.3	-93.5			17SR02	6.5	-157.4		
17MC04	5.8	-94.0	6.1	-93.8	17SR02	6.3	-160.1		
17MC05	6.6	-93.6			17SR02	6.3	-161.3	6.3	-160.7
17MC05	6.6	-93.8	6.6	-93.7	17SR04	8.0	-182.7		
17MC11	10.5	-137.1			17SR04	8.1	-184.3	8.1	-183.5
17MC11	11.0	-134.5	10.8	-135.8	RT1-2015	6.2	-174.1		
17MC16	1.1	-118.1			RT1-2015	6.4	-176.6		
17MC16	1.2	-115.0	1.1	-116.5	RT1-2015	6.3	-176.6	6.3	-175.8
17MC17	1.4	-96.8			RT10-2015	5.9	-162.8		
17MC17	1.4	-97.5			RT10-2015	5.7	-165.0		

17MC17	1.3	-96.7	1.4	-97.0	RT10-2015	5.9	-165.4	5.8	-164.4
17SC12	1.9	-128.9			RT11-2015	6.9	-156.2		
17SC12	1.9	-133.6			RT11-2015	6.9	-154.7	6.9	-155.4
17SC12	1.9	-134.6	1.9	-134.1	RT12-2015	6.3	-165.0		
17SC14	2.9	-140.7			RT12-2015	6.2	-163.9	6.3	-164.4
17SC14	3.0	-144.5	3.0	-142.6	RT13-2015	8.2	-166.5		
17SC17	1.5	-135.9			RT13-2015	8.0	-166.5	8.1	-166.5
17SC17	2.7	-121.5	2.1	-128.7	RT14-2015	8.2	-147.8		
17SC19	4.1	-136.3			RT14-2015	7.3	-145.1	7.7	-146.4
17SC19	4.2	-139.0	4.2	-137.6	RT17-2015	6.0	-152.1		
17SC27	1.7	-148.4			RT17-2015	5.3	-153.7		
17SC27	1.5	-142.6	1.6	-145.5	RT17-2015	6.6	-154.1	6.0	-153.3
17SC28	1.0	-137.1			RT18-2015	4.9	-169.3		
17SC28	1.0	-137.2			RT18-2015	6.2	-172.8	5.6	-171.1
17SC28	1.0	-139.9	1.0	-138.1	RT2-2015	6.5	-164.6		
17SC29	2.5	-155.1			RT2-2015	6.8	-166.6	6.6	-165.6
17SC29	2.7	-157.4	2.6	-156.3	RT5-2015	7.1	-181.1		
17SC30	5.5	-157.3			RT5-2015	7.3	-182.4	7.2	-181.7
17SC30	4.9	-156.6	5.2	-156.9	RT9-2015	6.7	-142.6		
17SC32	5.4	-93.2			RT9-2015	6.5	-145.7	6.6	-144.1
17SC32	4.9	-91.4	5.1	-92.3	TVI	6.4	-152.4		
17SC33	6.8	-126.0			TVI	7.3	-151.6	6.9	-152.0
17SC33	6.7	-126.5			TVM	4.1	-170.6		
17SC33	5.8	-127.6	6.4	-126.7	TVM	4.5	-171.0		
17SC34	0.9	-129.2			TVM	4.6	-172.8	4.4	-171.5
17SC34	1.3	-130.6	1.1	-129.9	TVN	4.6	-165.0		
17SC39	6.4	-134.3			TVN	4.3	-164.1	4.5	-164.6
17SC39	6.4	-137.3			TVR	3.8	-103.2		
17SC39	6.4	-138.4	6.4	-136.7	TVR	4.1	-106.6	3.9	-104.9

Table S3. XRF major element contents of selected tuff samples from southwestern Montana

Sample ID	Analysis *	Na ₂ O (%)	MgO (%)	Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	SiO ₂ (%)	K ₂ O (%)	CaO (%)	TiO ₂ (%)	MnO (%)	Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	Age (Ma)	δD _{vg} (‰; VSMOW)
RT2-2015	(1)	1.91	0.47	11.82	60.95	5.81	1.38	0.35	0.10	1.82		
	(2)	1.17	0.51	11.89	60.94	5.79	1.38	0.35	0.10	1.83		
	(3)	1.43	0.47	11.65	60.98	5.77	1.38	0.35	0.10	1.83		
	Average	1.51	0.48	11.79	60.96	5.79	1.38	0.35	0.10	1.82		
	Normalized	1.79	0.57	14.00	72.42	6.88	1.64	0.41	0.12	2.17	26±5	-165.6
RT5-2015	(1)	1.20	1.48	11.51	52.17	1.27	4.20	1.06	0.16	8.60		
	(2)	1.26	1.43	11.56	52.28	1.27	4.19	1.06	0.16	8.61		
	(3)	1.71	1.66	11.55	52.07	1.26	4.21	1.07	0.17	8.59		
	Average	1.39	1.52	11.54	52.17	1.26	4.20	1.06	0.17	8.60		
	Normalized	1.70	1.86	14.09	63.69	1.54	5.13	1.30	0.20	10.50	25±5	-181.7
RT9-2015	(1)	1.44	0.83	11.49	55.24	3.08	1.69	0.56	0.12	3.01		
	(2)	1.19	0.97	11.68	55.47	3.08	1.69	0.56	0.12	3.01		
	(3)	0.93	0.86	11.69	55.21	3.08	1.69	0.56	0.12	3.00		
	Average	1.19	0.89	11.62	55.30	3.08	1.69	0.56	0.12	3.01		
	Normalized	1.54	1.14	15.00	71.40	3.97	2.19	0.72	0.16	3.88	36±2	-144.1
RT11-2015	(1)	1.59	0.62	10.71	58.54	4.17	1.35	0.30	0.08	1.71		
	(2)	1.47	0.59	10.68	58.54	4.16	1.35	0.30	0.08	1.70		
	(3)	1.37	0.62	10.72	58.66	4.18	1.36	0.30	0.08	1.72		
	Average	1.48	0.61	10.70	58.58	4.17	1.36	0.30	0.08	1.71		
	Normalized	1.87	0.77	13.55	74.16	5.28	1.72	0.38	0.10	2.17	27±3	-155.4
RT12-2015	(1)	1.68	0.82	11.94	58.03	4.16	1.73	0.51	0.06	2.88		
	(2)	1.23	1.03	11.87	58.13	4.18	1.74	0.50	0.07	2.85		
	(3)	1.98	1.03	11.93	58.03	4.18	1.74	0.51	0.07	2.87		
	Average	1.63	0.96	11.91	58.06	4.17	1.74	0.51	0.07	2.87		
	Normalized	1.99	1.17	14.54	70.89	5.09	2.12	0.62	0.08	3.50	27±5	-164.4
RT13-2015	(1)	1.41	0.49	11.43	56.84	2.89	2.31	0.52	0.12	5.77		
	(2)	1.75	0.47	11.46	56.73	2.90	2.32	0.51	0.12	5.78		
	(3)	1.52	0.46	11.55	56.77	2.91	2.32	0.52	0.12	5.76		
	Average	1.56	0.47	11.48	56.78	2.90	2.32	0.52	0.12	5.77		

	Normalized	1.90	0.58	14.01	69.32	3.54	2.83	0.63	0.15	7.04	33.5±1	-166.5
RT14-2015	(1)	1.06	1.13	11.34	55.82	3.45	1.58	0.36	0.10	3.42		
	(2)	1.23	1.10	11.33	55.69	3.43	1.57	0.36	0.10	3.43		
	(3)	1.16	1.14	11.41	55.81	3.46	1.58	0.36	0.10	3.42		
	Average	1.15	1.12	11.36	55.77	3.45	1.58	0.36	0.10	3.42		
	Normalized	1.47	1.43	14.50	71.21	4.41	2.01	0.46	0.13	4.37	32.5±1	-146.4
RT17-2015	(1)	2.22	0.45	11.66	61.16	8.44	0.73	0.18	0.11	2.11		
	(2)	1.78	0.44	11.61	61.17	8.42	0.73	0.18	0.11	2.11		
	(3)	1.67	0.49	11.64	61.13	8.38	0.73	0.18	0.11	2.11		
	Average	1.89	0.46	11.64	61.15	8.42	0.73	0.18	0.11	2.11		
	Normalized	2.18	0.52	13.42	70.55	9.71	0.84	0.20	0.13	2.44	27±5	-153.3
RT18-2016	(1)	2.05	0.47	12.74	52.07	5.82	1.37	0.47	0.12	2.94		
	(2)	1.62	0.48	12.79	52.30	5.80	1.37	0.47	0.12	2.94		
	(3)	2.27	0.49	12.76	52.22	5.79	1.37	0.47	0.12	2.95		
	Average	1.98	0.48	12.77	52.20	5.80	1.37	0.47	0.12	2.95		
	Normalized	2.53	0.62	16.34	66.81	7.43	1.75	0.60	0.15	3.77	34±2	-171.1

* Due to the loss on ignition, the contents were normalized to 100%.

Figure S1. Geological map of the Sage Creek Basin, southwestern Montana. White circles with numbers indicate sample locations: 1, lower Sage Creek Member; 2, upper Sage Creek Member; 3, Dell Member; 4, Cook Ranch Member; 5, Blacktail Creek Member. Modified from Lonn et al. (2000).

Figure S2. Stratigraphic columns of the Sage Creek Basin from Schwartz and Graham (2017) to show stratigraphic heights of collected volcanic glass samples.

Figure S3. Field photos of sampled locations in the Sage Creek (A–E) and Jefferson (F–H) basins. Abbreviations: Fm.-formation; M.-member.

Figure S4. Field photos of sampled locations in the Muddy Creek (A–B), Flint Creek (C–D), Smith River (E–F) and Big Hole Valley (G–H) basins